

CarE-Service

**Circular economy business models
for innovative hybrid and electric mobility through
advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services**

ANALYSIS AND SPECIFICATIONS OF RE-USE VAUE CHAINS

(Deliverable 1.5)

Authors: Elena Mossali (CNR)
Nicoletta Picone (CNR)
Marcello Colledani (CNR)

Contributin Authors: Erik Sundin (LIU)
Fulvio Ardente (JRC)
Franco Di Persio (JRC)
Luigi De Rocchi (COBAT)

www.careserviceproject.eu

[@CarE_Service_EU](https://twitter.com/CarE_Service_EU)

[CarE_Service_EU](https://www.facebook.com/CarE_Service_EU)

[CarE-Service_EU](https://www.linkedin.com/company/CarE-Service_EU)

Join our "Stakeholders' Group" and
"Consumers' Committee"

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant No 776851*

Project Consortium

CNR	<i>Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche</i>	Italy
LIU	<i>Linkopings Universitet</i>	Sweden
ENV	<i>Envirobot Espana Sl</i>	Spain
PROD	<i>Prodigientia - Tecnologias De Informacao Sa</i>	Portugal
CSIC	<i>Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas</i>	Spain
C-ECO	<i>Circular Economy Solutions Gmbh</i>	Germany
COBAT	<i>Cobat Servizi</i>	Italy
FCA	<i>Fiat Chrysler Automobiles Italy Spa</i>	Italy
RAD	<i>Radici Novacips Spa</i>	Italy
IMA	<i>IMA Materialforschung Und Anwendungstechnik Gmbh</i>	Germany
Fraunhofer	<i>Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Foerderung Der Angewandten Forschung E.V.</i>	Germany
AVIC	<i>Avicenne Developpement</i>	France
CIA	<i>Cia Automation And Robotics Srl</i>	Italy
EVAI	<i>E-Vai Srl</i>	Italy
JRC	<i>JRC - Joint Research Centre European Commission</i>	Belgium

Executive Summary

This report presents a preliminary analysis of the three re-use value-chains (battery, metals and techno-polymers) of CarE-Service Project in order to derive specific process requirements to be further implemented and demonstrated.

The main objective is to propose an optimal management of End of Life (EoL) Electric and Hybrid Electric Vehicles (E&HEV), requiring proper technologies and *ad hoc* processes. The aim is the reduction of wasted materials in landfills or incinerators and the recovery of components with residual properties as re-used products or chemical compounds as secondary raw materials. In particular, the automotive target parts are:

- batteries, representing the main innovation in E&HEVs;
- techno-polymers, whose amount is increased to reduce the whole weight of E&HEVs; and
- metals.

To properly derive robust requirements addressing real needs for future sustainability, a great effort has been spent involving all relevant actors for the development of innovative technical solutions for future services at all supply chain levels. Therefore, State of Art analysis and in-depth interviews have been carried out with the key-players of the future de-manufacturing value-chains. Once collected all the information, several potential scenarios have been analysed and detailed schemes of the three main value-chains have been defined.

Finally, an in-sight view of the current re-design practices and European laws and directives addressing the EoL of automotive products is drawn to identify the limits concretely bounding the market exploitation of CarE-Service results.

List of Acronyms

AC Alternative Current

AHSS Advanced High Strength Steel

ASR Automotive Shredder Residue

DC Direct Current

E&HEV Electric and Hybrid Electric Vehicle

ELV End of Life Vehicle

EoL End of Life

EV Electric Vehicle

HRC Human-Robot Collaborative

ICE Internal Combustion Engine

LIB Lithium-Ion Battery

OEM Original Equipment Manufacturer

PA Polyamide

R&I Research and Innovation

SG Stakeholders Group

SMM Smart Mobile Module

Table of Content

A vertical diagram showing five circular nodes connected by a line, each corresponding to a table of contents entry. The nodes are white with a green border and a grey inner circle containing the page number. The entries are: 1. Introduction (P. 5), 2. Analysis of the State of the Art (P. 7), 3. Industrial Scenario description for the vaue-chain (P. 18), 4. Key results (P. 30), and Conclusion (P. 31).

<i>P. 5</i>	1. Introduction
<i>P. 7</i>	2. Analysis of the State of the Art
<i>P. 18</i>	3. Industrial Scenario description for the vaue-chain
<i>P. 30</i>	4. Key results
<i>P. 31</i>	Conclusion

1 INTRODUCTION

In the preliminary phase of CarE-Service Project, the three identified value-chains (batteries, metals and techno-polymers) have been assessed in order to derive the requirements for re-use, remanufacturing and recycling processes and technologies. The development of new technical solutions is joined by the analysis of potential changes in regulation and legislation and the review of re-design guidelines of E&HEV components.

1.1 Concepts and Methods

After having defined a common approach, in-depth interviews have been carried out with key-players of the future re-use value-chains (both Consortium partner and members of the project SG) to outline precise industrial scenarios for the final demonstration of CarE-Service project feasibility. Interviewed participants described their actual businesses and processes and were requested to imagine in a short and long-term future the desirable innovation in terms of technical advancements and new market opportunities for E&HEV components based on Circular Economy.

OBJECTIVES

- The definition of the current State of Art of recycling processes in automotive sector (techno-polymer and metallic components) and for Li-ion batteries.
- The identification of standards and regulations currently impacting and/or limiting the proposal of innovative solutions for end-of-life E&HEVs.
- The preliminary analysis and detection of guidelines for the re-design of products in order to make them easily disassemblable, re-usable and/or recyclable.
- The collection of possible innovative solutions to be developed during CarE-Service project.
- The identification of general requirements of processes, necessary for their application in real life.

1.2 Structure of the report

In Section 2, a State of the Art analysis has been reported in order to define a clear framework for the three-analysed value-chains (i.e. batteries, metals, techno-polymers), including:

- the description of current and common practices, technologies and processes for re-use, re-manufacturing and recycling of automotive components;
- the re-design approach as new collaborative methodology to enable the disassembly, remanufacturing and recycling of E&HEVs products;
- the analysis of current regulation and legislation addressing the EoL of automotive products, in order to identify the limits concretely bounding the market exploitation of CarE-Service results.

In Section 3, CarE-Service industrial scenarios description for the three value-chains have been reported, focusing on the innovation proposed with respect to the current situation. This section outlines also the importance of the re-design approach to make CarE-Service outcomes technically feasible and economically sustainable. Moreover, suggestions to address legislative barriers have been proposed in order to increase the CarE-Service results market exploitation.

2 ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF ART

The State of Art of a product, a process or a scientific field represents the more advanced results achieved till now in terms of device features, optimized technologies and operating parameters of a process or specific research activities and demonstrations.

A detailed State of Art analysis was conducted and reported in this section, with the objective to identify the technologies, processes and methodologies currently implemented, both at pilot scale and industrial level, to treat EoL automotive components. This analysis is aimed to identify issues, gaps and challenges of wasted E&HEV, for creating future opportunities and making procedures and technologies robust and easily available.

What happens to a vehicle when its life-cycle is over?

How is the variability of components and materials inside cars addressed at their end of life?

What are the main actors of the automotive sector for the treatment of EoL vehicles?

2.1 Strategies to address challenges of ELV and automotive recycling industry

By literature, around 86% in weight of materials from ELVs is reused, recycled or used for energy recovery, therefore automobiles represent one of the most recycled consumer products at current state of art [1].

In a conventional **Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) vehicle**, the procedure to manage waste materials includes the following steps:

1. Depollution: it includes the removal of various components and materials as:
 - i. fluids are drained to reduce hazards and environmental leakages;
 - ii. hazardous materials removal (lead battery, components containing mercury, etc.);
 - iii. tyres and airbags;

2. Hazardous materials removal (lead battery, components containing mercury, etc.);
3. Visual inspection and removal of parts to be reused or recycled with precise well-established treatments: if parts maintain their functionalities, they could be dismantled and sold as recovered components by scrap dealers, otherwise they are recycled;
4. Testing of reusable parts to be sold in a secondary market.
5. Crushing and shredding of the remaining car hulk: ELV body is shredded and separated in non-ferrous metals, ferrous metals and fluffs (i.e. Automotive Shredded Residue mainly composed by non-recyclable plastics, glass and rubber) fractions.

At European level, the ELV Directive 2000/53/EC sets the general management of wasted vehicles and **the established route** is represented by dismantling and testing of reusable components, well-known recycling of some specific parts and final shredding for steel recovery [1-4]. However, the introduction of EVs in automotive recycling market can lead to new challenges in terms of hazardous components, disassembly policies and regulations on materials management and transport.

Although EVs and ICE vehicles may appear externally equivalent, because born as adaptation of already existing automotive models, **significant changes** are introduced to manage two different working mechanisms, as reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Main components of ICE vehicles (red); main components of electric motors (green).

In EVs the combustion engine is substituted by the battery (storing chemical energy to convert into electrical one), the electric motor (AC or DC mode) and the controller (managing the supplied current) [5, 6].

mainly motivated by the increasing volume of the potential residual value of innovative components as embodied in EVs. The activities focus on batteries, techno-polymer

components and metal parts, of which is reported below a brief overview on current applied processes.

2.1.1 Battery value-chain

Lithium-Ion battery (LIB) represents one of the main elements of EVs structure, as much as the highest valuable component of this type of cars. The main advantages of LIBs are their **high weight/power** and **weight/energy ratios**, **reduced memory effect** and **minimal loss of charge at rest** [7].

Although the volume of EVs is rapidly increasing, a set of **standardized safety procedure** for battery removal from EV's has not been identified yet because the current small collection volume of wasted automotive LIBs does not push OEMs and dismantler to face this issue. According to the state of the art, EoL portable LIBs are transported inside ad hoc containers, covered by vermiculite to avoid flame propagation, till recycling plant, where valuable metals are recovered through the process reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Typical recycling process for metals recovery from wasted LIBs.

Initially, batteries are sorted according to their chemistry and, once isolated, LIBs are discharged through short circuit induction or thermal treatments to evaporate flammable solvents and deactivate Lithium. The dismantling phase is performed on LIBs packs to remove plastic external housing, electronics (i.e. cables, BMS, etc.), connectors and external cooling systems [9-14].

LIBs comminution is aimed to liberate and separate active materials (i.e. metals oxides) from current collector foils of Aluminium and Copper through costs-saving physical methods. This step is generally performed in proper salts solutions or with inert atmosphere to minimize safety issues caused by the residual charge and chemical hazard. Drying is an optional step to eliminate the remaining electrolyte and is followed by a separation step

performed through magnetic classification, air-classification and/or vibrating screen technique to concentrate target metals in a proper fraction [9, 15, 17-19].

Pyro-metallurgical treatments exploit high temperatures to decompose, reduce or evaporate metals. Conversely, hydrometallurgical route is a leaching treatment able to transfer target metals into liquid phase through acidic solutions, allowing a good recovery with high purity and low energy consumption [8, 20-21]. After extraction, aqueous solutions are purified through electrolysis, solvent extraction, ion exchange, precipitation or cementation techniques [8].

Concerning **LIBs reuse or remanufacturing**, nowadays no standardized policies or procedures to properly dismantle, test and certificate wasted batteries are defined. Wasted E&HEV LIBs could be reused and remanufactured for different secondary stationary applications thanks to their high residual capacity ($\approx 80\%$).

CarE-Service project is aimed to face current criticalities in LIBs treatment, supporting dismantling facilities in securing battery packs from E&HEV, testing residual functionalities to exploit battery pack/module/cell reuse and setting process parameters for remanufacturing and recycle of LIBs. Existing barriers will be deeply analysed and studied to propose and demonstrate new technical solutions technologically advanced, environmental-friendly and economically feasible.

2.1.2 Techno-polymer value-chain

Techno-polymers are the polymer materials used to produce any plastic component where the requested characteristics, such as mechanical, thermal and chemical, are higher than those offered from the common polymers. In the automotive sector, they are appreciated due to corrosion resistance, flexibility and resilience properties for safety devices (i.e. airbags and seat belts), good thermal insulation, reduced noise and optimal space utilization [22].

Techno-polymers are mainly used in E&HEVs to replace metals, allowing a weight reduction and generally a lower energy consumption (during production and operation). Moreover, they are appreciated due to corrosion resistance, flexibility and resilience properties for safety devices (i.e. airbags and seat belts), good thermal insulation, reduced

noise and optimal space utilization. Anyway, techno-polymers components could incur in **degradation phenomena** that affect and decrease their original performances due to:

- UV light;
- Temperature gradient;
- Mechanical stresses;
- Chemical contact with strong acids and basis;
- High moisture absorption rate.

Sunlight radiation, for example, acts on chemical structure and molecular orientation of polyamide (PA), causing chain scissions and the loss of material properties (i.e. increased viscosity, decreased strength and elongation, discoloration and fading of coloured materials). The only way to increase polymeric resistance to these external degradations is the use of additives during material formulation to make the final product more stable, according to its specific application [25, 26]. To reduce the amount of wasted polymeric products, universities, research institutes and plastics companies are investing in R&I to find new technical solutions able to recover the material. However, the reintroduction of recycled materials into the market is not so easy due lower material purity, aesthetical problems and overall uncertainty on the technical properties [27, 28].

The most common **PA recycling process** is reported in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Typical recycling process for techno-polymers recovery from wasted LIBs.

PA products, such as carpets, are generally recycled into two different ways due to their hazardousness if landfilled (i.e. they cause huge fires containing dangerous gases):

1. Physical recycling: the process has two stages, melting and pelletizing for subsequent injection molding, but causes a loss of material quality (i.e. decreased tensile and impact strength). When melting is obtained by extrusion technique, mechanical and metallurgical features results better and if a twin screw is used, also surface properties are enhanced. This recycling process is characterized by technical viability, acceptable costs and environmental benefits.
2. Chemical recycling: more complex and economically expensive, it was firstly performed by DuPont in 1944 and consists in a depolymerization (i.e. long polymer chains disintegration into caprolactam monomers by acidolysis, aminolysis, hydrolysis or catalyzed depolymerization in vacuum) followed by a new polymerization. During depolymerization a slurry is formed through water addition and, after density separation, a new material with 98.5% purity is obtained.

Despite these routes are well known, studies are currently performed on their parameters to optimize the process and to generalize it also for EoL products more complex in terms of chemical compositions [29-31].

Considering automotive sector, there are lots of different plastics inside a car and the cost to separate and clean each polymer is not economically sustainable right now. Currently, polymeric and composite components contribute to the Automotive Shredder Residue (ASR) and are mainly treated by energy recovery, but this not represents a long-term environmentally feasible solution because plastics amount is continuously increasing (i.e. from 6% in 1970 to 16% in 2010 and to predicted 18% in 2020) both to be treated in EoL vehicles and to be produced for new automotive demand. CarE-Service project challenge for this value-chain is to propose sustainable technical solutions for PA techno-polymers reuse and recycling, avoiding thermal recovery strategies [32, 33].

2.1.3 Metal parts value-chain

Metallic materials represent $\approx 80\%$ of automotive total weight given by:

- Steel (i.e. section profiles, car body sheets, engine components, etc.);
- Non-ferrous metals including:
 - Copper (e.g. in electronic components);
 - Aluminium alloys (i.e. body frame, doors, pedals, steering wheels, gearbox housing, cooling system components, etc.);
 - Magnesium alloys (casted components, i.e. steering wheels, intake manifold, oil

According to World Steel Association, the automotive sector accounts for 12% of global steel consumption (e.g. in 2007 a car had 1'090 kg of steel), particularly Advanced High Strength Steels (AHSS), due to its mechanical properties and high recycling efficiency. However, new requirements of lightweight and cost-effective materials increase the amount of Aluminium and Magnesium alloys, characterized by low specific weight, improved crash energy absorbing properties, ease of processability and high recyclability [34-37].

Currently, all main metal parts are sent to **recycling process** after shredding procedure and are subjected to metal extraction process reported in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Current recycling process of steel scraps, including those collected by EoL car bodies.

Sorting allows to concentrate metal elements and to properly set recycling technologies parameters. Shredding is necessary to promote subsequent melting, increasing surface to volume ratio and decreasing required energy, while large furnaces are used to fuse metal according to input materials:

- Blast furnaces use scrap as additional element to raw materials;
- Electric arc furnaces are almost completely based on scrap addition.

Finally, after electrolysis to remove any contaminants in metal slag, the output material is solidified in bars to be easily reused in new applications [38-40].

The recycling of 1 ton of steel helps to save 1.8 barrels of oil, 115 million kJ of generated heat, 642 kWh of energy, and 2.3 m³ of landfill space, so that nearly 40% of worldwide steel production is made by using recycled steel (≈400 million tons/year) [38-40].

Even if the forming processes are well-understood and have high level of process stability, they still are quite sensitive towards mechanical and dimensional properties of pre-materials.

Due to time-consuming tuning and the needs to preventively know material properties, pre-used materials are not yet processed on an industrial scale at all. The only forming operation which is common in the automotive branch is the repair of minor damaged sheet metal parts by non-automated, mostly manual, forming processes. The innovation pursued by CarE-Service project focuses on the introduction of reforming processes to recover selected metal parts at the EoL of the vehicle, shaped again for up-graded vehicles, new E&HEV components or other applications outside automotive sector.

2.2 Re-design approach in automotive sector

When it comes to the different EoL strategies, the waste hierarchy (Figure 5) is often referred to a precise terminology, explaining the possible EoL operations.

Figure 5: The EoL hierarchy illustrating different operations for a product when reaching its End-of-Life. It is here assumed that the options higher in the hierarchy are preferable in comparison to the lower ones.

- **Reduce** (i.e. minimize the amount of waste through a proper re-design of products);
- **Reuse** (i.e. use something again with the same purpose of the original product);
- **Upgrading** (i.e. increase the quality or the functionality of the product), **Repair** (i.e. returning broken products back to the usable state) or **Remanufacturing** (i.e. restoring of product performances to “as new” conditions, with same warranty of new products);
- **Recycle** (i.e. convert waste products into new objects, extracting secondary raw materials);
- **Energy recovery** (i.e. convert waste into energy, as heat or electricity);
- **Disposal** (i.e. action or process of getting rid of something).

Reuse operations preserve at the best the value of the parts and can reduce as well environmental burdens compared to lower options (i.e. recycling, energy recovery and

disposal) that cause a downgrade of components. The EoL hierarchy is aimed to prioritize alternatives with the lower ratio effort/energy, therefore reuse operations are preferably chosen to treat EoL products.

The main objective of most product designers is to ensure optimal features preferability in manufacturing and use of their products, leaving the EoL stage far less prioritized. Some reasons for this are that the product life cycle stages of manufacturing and use are closer in time to the product design than the EoL stage and they are easier to control, simulate and demonstrate. However, in order to meet the future demand of the EoL operations there are several **design strategies** to choose from, as described in Table 1.

Product Design for:	Strategy's Goal	Recovery Operations	Operation's Goal	Output quality vs OR
Preventive Maintenance	Enable use extension	Cleaning, diagnosis, product specific overhauling activities to rise quality levels up to OR and test	To retain a product's functional capabilities and/or cosmetic condition	Similar or lower
Upgrading (Hardware)		Cleaning, diagnosis, disassembly, modules replacement, reassembly, testing	Enhancing, relative to the original design specifications, a product's functional capabilities and or cosmetic condition	Higher for the upgraded modules
Repairing – Corrective Maintenance and Breakdown Maintenance	Product/part reuse	Core collection, diagnosis, cleaning, disassembly, specific component remediation, reassembly, testing	Correction of specific faults to bring a product back to working or cosmetic conditions	Similar or lower
Refurbishing or Reconditioning		Core collection, diagnosis, cleaning, disassembly, storage, product repair/remediation, reassembly, testing	Bring back to working or cosmetic condition	Similar or lower
Remanufacturing		Core collection, diagnosis, cleaning, disassembly, storage, product repair/remediation, reassembly, testing	Bring product back to original performance specifications	OR or higher
Part harvesting	Part reuse	Part collection, diagnosis, cleaning, disassembly, storage, repair/remediation, reassembly, testing	Collection of working product's parts for new products	OR or higher
Material recycling	Material reuse	Collect used and broken products, parts, materials	Bring back materials for use	Similar or lower

Table 1: Design strategies for End-of-Life operations (adapted from Pozo Arcos et al 2017 [41]) [42-47]. "OR = original requirements".

Many different design strategies are available in function of different objectives and quality outputs. Some design approaches are aimed to achieve products having similar or higher properties than the original ones (e.g. remanufacturing), while others have the goal to maintain initial requirements or to avoid an excessive properties loss (e.g. reuse or material recycling).

The re-design approach within CarE-Service project is aimed to follow product **(re)design guidelines**, whenever possible. Specific and adapted guidelines will be selected for each value-chain, according to identified EoL operations for reuse, remanufacturing and recycling of E&HEV batteries, techno-polymers and metal parts. Any criticality practically found during technical solutions implementation will be addressed to a possible solution thanks to a proper redesign of the product.

2.3 Analysis of the current regulations

An in-depth analysis of the European laws and directives has been performed by the CarE-Service Consortium, addressing the EoL automotive products and considering several aspects: safety, transport, storage and environmental implications towards second-use applications and recycling. The output of this analysis is summarized in Table 2.

EU Norm	Field of Application	Practical Implication
Directive 2000/53/EC, partially amended by Directive 2018/849	Management of End of Life Vehicle (ELV). Sets targets for re-use, recycling and recovery of ELV.	Consolidated EU Law 2006/12/CE Directive 2008/98/CE
Directive 2005/64/EC	Sets targets for re-usability and recyclability	Council Directive 70/156/EEC
Consolidated EU law 2006/12/CE	General Environmental Law	Directive 2000/53/EC Directive 2006/66/EC Directive 2008/98/CE Decision 2002/532/EC
REACH Regulation: EC 1907/2006	Protection of human and environmental health from risks deriving from chemicals	Directive 2006/66/EC Directive 2006/12/CE Directive 2002/532/EC
Consolidated EU law 2006/12/CE (further modifications)	General Environmental Law	Directive 2000/53/EC Directive 2006/66/EC (Battery) Directive 2008/98/CE (End of Waste) Decision 2002/532/EC (EWC code and Waste characterization)

Directive 2006/66/EC, partially amended by Directive 2018/849/EC	Spent portable batteries; Spent Industrial batteries (included Li-ion automotive battery)	Consolidated EU Law 2006/12/CE 2002/532/EC Basel Convention REACH
Basel Convention (1013/2006 EC)+Correlation table 2016/1245 EEC+ADR Reg.	Transportation between EU countries; Packaging of “dangerous” goods	Directive 2002/532/EC Directive 2006/12/CE
Regulation 1013/2006	Waste shipment regulation; ELV shipment	Directive 1013/2006 and Correspondents' Guidelines N°9 on shipment of EoL vehicles
Directive 2008/98/CE amended by Directive 2018/851/EC	Best Practice to declare “waste” as “new raw materials or similar”	ELV Directive Battery Directive WEEE Directive CE n. 333/2011 (Metallic Scraps)
EU Directive 493/2012 CE	Requirements for the “efficient recycling process”	Directive 2006/66/EC Directive 2006/12/CE

Table 2: Relevant legislation for the CarE-Service circular economy for e-mobility solution.

Even if the aforementioned laws create a general framework for the re-use, remanufacturing and recycling of automotive parts (including E&HEVs components), in some cases such laws do not focus on all waste streams and they are not fully consistent with the Circular Economy principles.

In addition, the so called “ELVs of unknown whereabouts” phenomena should be considered: it refers to the large quantity of ELVs disappearing from Europe (i.e. from 3.4 to 4.6 million vehicles per year), not reported as being exported nor treated officially as ELVs, equivalent to “unknown whereabouts”.

To this purpose, and also to address other criticalities, the Commission has a legal obligation to “review the ELV Directive, by 31 December 2020, and to this end, shall submit a report to the European Parliament and the Council, accompanied, if appropriate, by a legislative proposal”. The Commission is currently carrying out an **evaluation of the ELV Directive** to analyse its implementation and to assess whether it has met its original objectives.

In addition, the **EU’s Plastics Strategy** launched in January 2018 refers to the automotive sector as a significant source of plastic waste that could be recycled and to its good potential for uptake of recycled content. It includes under its actions the assessment of regulatory or economic incentives for the uptake, in particular in the context of the evaluation/review of the ELV Directive, and should look into the influence and interaction of newly arising

challenges, aligning with other legislative instruments, such as the Batteries Directive or the WEEE Directive.

The Commission is currently carrying out also the evaluation of the **Battery Directive** to assess the actual performance of the Directive compared to initial expectations. Environmental aspects, resource efficiency and new developments in battery types, as well as applications and recycling technologies will be addressed in the revision of the Directive, including aspects such as the re-use of battery, the battery labelling and removal. Targets for collection and recycling also should be reviewed and the reporting system methodology should be harmonized and improved. A new version of the Directive is expected by 2020.

3 INDUSTRIAL SCENARIO DESCRIPTION FOR THE THREE VALUE-CHAINS

The CarE-Service project aims to demonstrate **innovative circular economy business models based on advanced mobility services**, exploiting E&HEVs. Such business models will entail the re-use, remanufacturing and recycling of components and materials of E&HEV for applications in the automotive sector and in other sectors (i.e. energy, plastics, mechanical, furniture, etc.) (Figure 6).

Figure 6: CarE-Service overall concept ecosystem.

In order to achieve this ambitious objective, a set of new technological solutions will be engineered and demonstrated, and new approaches for re-design and regulations will be proposed. In particular, the developed solutions and approaches:

- 1) will enable new re-use, recycling and remanufacturing businesses for key added-value components of E&HEVs, such as batteries, techno-polymers and metal parts;
- 2) will enable the service offering processes:
 - innovative Smart Mobile Modules (SMMs) (i.e. trucks) equipped with advanced technologies for the on-site disassembly and characterization of key-components of vehicles;
 - a platform that will match demand and offering of high-value parts and E&HEV components;
 - the re-design of parts to be re-used and recycled, embedding also smart elements and sensors that can transmit information about their conditions in a logic of “Industry 4.0”;
 - new supply chain governance models and logistics schemes.

In this section, a detailed analysis of technical solutions to be developed and of potential changes in regulation and legislation is provided.

3.1 Technical solutions

In the following sections a detailed analysis of the target value-chains to be developed within the CarE-Service project is reported. The defined **process-chains** intersects with the value-chains views, providing a complete description of each demonstrator. This analysis will lay the foundation for the definition of the specific technological requirements of each process stage, evaluating the possibility to perform in plant or on-site treatment by using the SMMs, and also indicating the link with the CarE-Service Platform.

The identified technical solutions will be representative of the potentiality of CarE-Service view in an initial take-back scenario, corresponding to a transition phase from the current processes to steady-state conditions, and characterized by low volumes to be treated in SMMs. However, when the proposed approach will get to full capacity, in a high throughput

scenario, the operations will be fully performed in the dismantler facilities or in equipped plants and the SMMs will be used only for emergency conditions, acting as special procedure for particularly high-risk cases (e.g. severely damaged E&HEVs). A schematic view of these scenarios is represented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Differences between the initial transition phase characterized by a low throughput and the steady-state conditions, where the significant volumes of EV will be directly treated in situ and SMMs will be relevant just in emergency cases.

Furthermore, the technical solutions detailed in the next paragraphs are described separately for each process-chain, even if the possibility to parallelize the activities will be proved (e.g. the disassembly of polymeric components will occur together with battery extraction).

3.1.1 Battery value-chain

In Figure 8 is represented the proposed value-chain of EoL LIBs from automotive sector. The represented approach was developed deeply analysing the criticalities of currently used technical solutions and interviewing and sharing information with Consortium partners and SG members having expertise and competence in the battery value-chain.

Due to the chemical and the electrical hazardousness of this component, CarE-Service technical solutions are aimed at assisting dismantling facilities during disassembly stage, which is a crucial step for a safe LIBs handling, and for the assessment of the optimal strategy among reuse, remanufacturing or recycling.

Figure 8: Battery value-chain in CarE-Service project, showing actions to perform during LIBs management and roles of Consortium partners in each stage.

In the following, a list of the main operations of the proposed CarE-Service battery value-chain is reported:

- semi-automated battery disassembly from the vehicle;
- visual inspection and preliminary testing;
- discharging;
- recycling of damaged pack/module/cell;
- reassembly of modules and cells for re-use;
- certification of new pack/module/cell for stationary applications;
- certification of secondary raw materials recovered by recycling processes.

The first operation to be performed with an EoL E&HEV is the **disassembly of battery** from the car to secure the following operations and the working place. The disassembly requires trained people and this procedure will be performed in SMMs. The aim of CarE-Service project for this operation is to partially automatize the procedure thanks to robotic technologies properly calibrated to face LIBs weight, dimensions, position in the automotive vehicle, component dangerousness and disassembly priority. The second objective is to test the battery inside the SMM in order to **recognize, roughly characterize and address LIBs** in a reasonable amount of time, preparing it for transportation to the specialized plant. After the testing, the EoL LIBs could be addressed to the following routes: 1. Pack reuse: if maintaining good residual performances; 2. Pack disassembly: going to module level; 3. Pack recycling: for materials recovery. The system is driven by secondary applications market, therefore the ratio reused-packs/disassembled-packs is proportional to the demand-offer target. For **pack reuse**, a deeper testing is performed to certificate the component for secondary market applications. For the **pack disassembly**, Human Robot Cooperation (HRC) technologies have been proposed to perform the case removal and the module disconnection. Additional and in depth tests are needed to address the LIB module to several routes: direct reuse, disassembly till cell level or recycling. As for battery packs, module re-manufacturing is driven by market demand in a pull approach. Finally, for **LIBs recycling** a combination of mechanical pre-treatment and hydrometallurgical process has been proposed, aiming to extract valuable metals as secondary raw materials.

3.1.2 Techno-polymers value-chain

Figure 9 illustrates the proposed value-chain for EoL automotive techno-polymer components.

Figure 9: Techno-polymer value-chain in CarE-Service project

Due to the high value and high performances of these parts, CarE-Service technical solutions aim to guide the choice between reuse and recycling routes. Proper inspection, characterization and disassembly steps will be able to define material status, process feasibility and economical revenue, according to the market demand.

In the following, a list of the main operation of the proposed CarE-Service techno-polymer value-chain is reported:

- visual inspection and preliminary testing for accessible polymer parts;
- semi-automated disassembly of PA parts from the vehicle: non-destructive disassembly approach for reusable components; destructive disassembly approach to dismantle parts to be recycled;
- testing: specific tests will be performed in plant in order to validate the reusability of components (degradation, deformation, etc.) and the recyclability (presence of additives and/or flame retardants affecting the recycling process);
- recycling of damaged techno-polymer parts;
- certification of secondary raw materials recovered by recycling processes;
- re-use of techno-polymer components as spare parts;
- certification of reusable techno-polymer component as spare part.

Preliminary steps performed inside SMMs are visual inspection and testing of parts focused on the identification of aesthetical and functional damages of the components.

Reusable components will be disassembled with non-destructive strategies to preserve their functionality. According to the identified value-chain, techno-polymer components are defined reusable only if: a market demand is present (i.e. pull strategy), the part results in good conditions after a visual inspection, and testing procedure ensures its functionality. When all these conditions are checked, parts are non-destructively disassembled, cleaned, certified and sold as spare parts.

Components not suitable for reuse are disassembled for **recycling** and sent to the plant for a proper material characterization. The target techno-polymer is the PA polymeric matrix, whose recognition is difficult due to material variability and to poor data marked on parts. If the component is PA made, it is disassembled through HRC technologies, otherwise it follows

conventional recovery routes not analysed in the CarE-Service project. For recyclable components disassembly will be destructive to be fast, efficient and inherently flexible.

After recycling process, **secondary produced PA** is used in new products for automotive sector, furniture or other applications. Recycled products cannot have a coloured texture without virgin material addition, but black components could be produced for non-visible applications or as filler and internal framework of non-automotive products. For high-value applications, requiring also higher mechanical and thermal properties, CarE-Service demonstrators will use specific amount of recycled material, to balance good technical performances and recycled features.

3.1.3 Metal parts value-chain

Figure 10 represents the proposed value-chain for EoL automotive metal parts.

Conversely to the current metal recycle through metallurgy, CarE-Service technical solution is aimed at reforming large automotive metal sheets (i.e. non-structural parts) to obtain new products for the automotive sector. Along with recycling route, disassembly and reuse with new joints are exploited on structural metal parts to increase their life cycle and to ensure profitability from their residual properties.

In the following, a list of the main operation of the proposed CarE-Service metal value-chain is reported:

- visual inspection for the identification of structural and non-structural parts;
- preliminary testing to characterize re-formable non-structural parts;
- semi-automated non-destructive disassembly of metal parts;
- testing: specific tests will be performed on the final reformed part or reassembled component;
- certification of reformed metal parts.

The first operation performed inside SMMs is a **visual inspection**, to distinguish re-formable non-structural parts from potentially reusable structural ones and to identify damages:

- severe damaged parts are directly sent to the steelworks, where they are melted and recycled through conventional metallurgical processes;
- potentially re-formable/reusable parts are selectively dismantled, tested and cleaned to be re-formed in new shape or re-assembled in new car models through properly designed joints.

Disassembly step is performed at two different levels:

- 1) in SMMs a rough dismantling of structural part isolates them from the car body, allowing selective components transportation into the plant;
- 2) in the plant, specific technologies are used to separate structural components, preparing their terminals to be joint again.

Once tested, non-structural parts are disassembled to be reformed: flat metal sheets, not heavily bent or deformed, are dismantled through HRC technologies and sent to the plant, while casted parts, not re-formable, are directly melt inside steelworks.

Metal parts are reformed through a press equipped with a proper forming tool. The reused metal sheet is forced to take the geometry modulated by the mold thanks to the application of a proper force, in agreement with material composition, geometry and thickness. The produced components could be again non-structural parts of E&HEVs or metallic objects not necessarily belonging to automotive sector. Finally, reformed products must be certified through geometry measurements and surface checks to adhere to Primary Part Approval Procedure by OEM.

Figure 10: Metal value-chain in CarE-Service project

3.2 Requirements and KPIs for the re-design approach

In previous sections, reuse, remanufacturing and recycling processes have been described for each value-chain. According to the identified process steps and the re-design guidelines, product re-design requirements are analysed, aimed at facilitating the different phases of CarE-Service technical solutions. In particular, in the following, examples of specific requirements for each process are reported.

DISASSEMBLY

Easy visible and accessible joints

Minimization of the number of parts and fasteners necessary for assembly, disassembly and reassembly

TESTING

Easy visible and accessible testing points

New products and software design, allowing testing time minimization

REMANUFACTURING

Inclusion of barcode or other data storage systems to minimize the time for part identification

Easiness to reprocess

RECYCLING

New products with higher content of recycled materials (legislation)

New technologies implementation to facilitate parts/materials separation

3.3 Regulation and legislation improvements in CarE-Service project

The current standardization and regulation framework is not fully optimized for the establishment of a clear and safe business environment supporting the diffusion of circular business models for E&HEVs. CarE-Service Consortium has already identified the legislation as potential risk for project results dissemination and exploitation. In fact, the following criticalities exist and should be carefully addressed during the project activities:

- regulations and standards can bound the re-use of hybrid and electric vehicles components in specific Member States;
- it is not clear how to consider the extended producer's responsibility with "second-life" products. The Original Equipment Manufacturer is not explicitly exempted from responsibilities after selling of reused parts by another organization, neither left out of responsibility for the end-of-life of the reused parts and refunded of the environmental fees and/or the financial guarantees already paid;
- the procedures for applying the "end of waste" classification to end-of-life batteries (or components such as modules and cells) for their re-use or re-production are not yet provided for by law;
- some pieces of legislation are not fully consistent with the principles and strategies of the Circular Economy;
- specific standard and policies are missing for measuring KPIs and conditions indicated in the regulation.
- there is a lack of communication standards. Existing coding systems do not provide standardized data structure for complete set of waste data. This contributes to supply chain fragmentation and to lack of interoperability of ICT systems of different vendors, with obvious negative consequences on the efficiency of circular economy value-chains.

4 KEY RESULTS

Through a deep knowledge of current processes and procedures for EoL vehicles, new technical solutions were developed, specifically targeted to peculiar EV components (i.e. batteries, techno-polymers and metals). Along with the proposal of innovative reuse, remanufacturing and recycling solutions, potential barriers were underlined in terms of design constraints and normative gaps.

KEY MESSAGES

- Despite automobiles are the most recycled consumer products, EVs lead to new challenges in terms of hazardous components, disassembly policies and regulations on materials management and transport.
- A set of standardized safety, recycling or remanufacturing procedures for EV **battery** has not been identified yet. EoL portable LIBs are generally recycled for valuable metals recovery through pyro-metallurgical processes.
- The reintroduction of recycled **techno-polymers** into the market is not easy, therefore currently polymeric and composite components are treated by energy recovery.
- Automotive **metal** parts are sent to process for metal recycling, while remanufacturing is not occurring yet.
- **CarE-Service project** is aimed at facilitating EV components recycling, remanufacturing and reuse through: i) semi-automated disassembly, ii) ad hoc testing of components to properly assess their reusability; iii) technical and economical sustainable recycling of damaged parts; iv) reassembly/reforming of specific components for re-use and v) certification of second life products/parts or secondary raw materials.
- A proper **re-design** of components could allow an easier management of EoL products, simplifying remanufacturing and recycling processes.
- The revision of existing legislations, not aligned with new products developments, and the integration of new standards and procedures are necessary for the implementation of safe and sustainable treatments for EoL EVs.

5 CONCLUSION

The three main value-chains (i.e. batteries, metals and techno-polymers) have been analysed, to be used as reference within the technical work of the project. In addition to the CarE-Service technical solutions, specific considerations have been carried out for products re-design approach and for regulation and legislation.

An in depth state of the art analysis has been performed with the objective to: i) define a clear framework for the three-analysed value-chains, starting from the description of the current and common practices, technologies and processes in the automotive sector; ii) analyse the advantages related to the application of a re-design approach; iii) analyse the current European laws and directives addressing the end of life of automotive products, by considering different aspects: safety, transport, storage and environmental implications towards second-use applications, and recycling.

Moreover, CarE-Service industrial scenarios have been defined, focusing on the innovation proposed with respect to current situation, as well as the analysis of limits in regulation and legislation potentially bounding the market exploitation of CarE-Service results.

Index of Tables

Table 1: Design strategies for End-of-Life operations (adapted from Pozo Arcos et al 2017 [41]) [42-47].

Table 2: Relevant norms and legislation for the CarE-Service circular economy for e-mobility solution.

Index of Figures

Figure 1: Main components of ICE vehicles (red); main components of electric motors (green).

Figure 2: Typical recycling process for metals recovery from wasted LIBs.

Figure 3: Typical recycling process for techno-polymers recovery from wasted LIBs.

Figure 4: Current recycling process of steel scraps, including those collected by EoL car bodies.

Figure 5: The EoL hierarchy illustrating different operations for a product when reaching its End-of-Life. It is here assumed that the options higher in the hierarchy are preferable in comparison to the lower ones.

Figure 6: CarE-Service overall concept ecosystem.

Figure 7: Differences between the initial transition phase characterized by a low throughput and the steady-state conditions, where the significant volumes of EV will be directly treated in situ and SMMs will be relevant just in emergency cases.

Figure 8: Battery value-chain in CarE-Service project, showing actions to perform during LIBs management and roles of Consortium partners in each stage.

Figure 9: Techno-polymer value-chain in CarE-Service project.

Figure 10: Metal value-chain in CarE-Service project.

References

- [1] Automotive Recycling Industry. Environmentally Friendly, Market Driven, and Sustainable. Automotive Recyclers Association (ARA), ISRI and Alliance of Automobile Manufacturers 2014, available online: <http://armmass.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/AutoRecyclingIndustry1.pdf>.
- [2] Leblanc R. Auto Recycling Recent Trends, Opportunities, and Challenges. The balance small business 2018, available online: <https://www.thebalancesmb.com/auto-recycling-recent-trends-opportunities-and-challenges-4011892>
- [3] Leblanc R. How Are Cars Recycled? The balance small business 2016, available online: <https://www.thebalancesmb.com/how-are-cars-recycled-2877944>
- [4] How we treat ELVs. European Group of Automotive Recycling Associations, available online: <https://www.egaranet.org/>
- [5] Brain M. How Electric Cars Work. Howstuffworks, available online: <https://auto.howstuffworks.com/electric-car.htm>.
- [6] Thaku A. Electric Cars. EngineersGarage, available online: <https://www.engineersgarage.com/articles/what-is-electric-cars-structure-working>.
- [7] Otto A. Battery management network for fully electrical vehicle featuring smart systems at cell and pack level. Fraunhofer Institute for Electronic Nano System ENAS, presentation of May 30, 2012.
- [8] Espinosa D.C.R.; Mansur M.B. Recycling batteries. In Waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) handbook; Goodship V., Stevels AB, Eds.; Woodhead Publishing Limited, UK, 2012; pp. 365-384, ISBN 978-0-85709-089-8.
- [9] Diekmann J.; Hanisch C.; Froböse L.; Schällicke G.; Loellhoeffel T.; Fölster A.; Kwade A. Ecological Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries from Electric Vehicles with Focus on Mechanical Processes, Journal of The Electrochemical Society 2017, 164, 1, A6184-A6191.

- [10] Wegener K.; Andrew S.; Raatz A.; Dröder K.; Herrmann C. Disassembly of Electric Vehicle Batteries Using the Example of the Audi Q5 Hybrid System, *Procedia CIRP* 2014, 23, 155-160.
- [11] Weyrich M.; Natkunarajah N. Conception of an automated plant for the disassembly of lithium ion batteries, *The 6th International Conference on Life Cycle Management in Gothenburg* 2013.
- [12] Herrmann C.; Raatz A.; Mennenga M.; Schmitt J.; Andrew S. Assessment of Automation Potentials for the Disassembly of Automotive Lithium Ion Battery Systems, *19th CIRP International Conference on Life Cycle Engineering, Berkeley*, 2012.
- [13] Schmitt J.; Haupt H.; Kurrat M.; Raatz A. Disassembly Automation for Lithium-Ion Battery Systems Using a Flexible Gripper, *The 15th International Conference on Advanced Robotics, Tallinn*, 2011.
- [14] Williard N.; Sood B.; Osterman M.; Pecht M. Disassembly methodology for conducting failure analysis on lithium-ion batteries, *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron* 2011, 22, 1616-1630.
- [15] Georgi-Maschler T.; Friedrich B.; Weyhe R.; Heegn H.; Rutz M. Development of a recycling process for Li-ion batteries, *Journal of Power Sources* 2012, 207, 173-182.
- [16] Lain M. J. Recycling of Lithium ion cells and batteries, *Journal of Power Sources* 2001, 97-98, 736-738.
- [17] Saloojee F.; Lloyd J. Lithium battery recycling process: a desktop study, *Crundwell Management Solutions*, 2015.
- [18] Wuschke L.; Jäckel H.; Peuker U. A.; Gellner M. Separation of electrode foils from li-ion traction batteries, *XXVIII International Mineral Processing Congress IMPC*, 2016.
- [19] Li J.; Shi P.; Wang Z.; Chen Y.; Chang C. A combined recovery process of metals in spent lithium-ion batteries, *Chemosphere* 2009, 77, 1132-1136.

- [20] Bankole O. E. Battery Recycling Technologies: Recycling Waste Lithium Ion Batteries with the Impact on the Environment In-View. *Journal of Environment and Ecology* 2013, 4, 1, 14-28.
- [21] Raham A.; Afroz R. Lithium Battery Recycling Management and Policy. *Int. J. Energy Technology and Policy* 2017, 13, 3, 278-291.
- [22] Automotive. The world moves with plastics. *PlasticsEurope AISBL* 2013.
- [23] COMPARE Project: Result In Brief. Recycling polyamide for automotive industry. 2005. Available online: https://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/80566_en.html
- [24] Nyamekye P. Re-use and Re-cycling of Automobile Plastics – A step to manage plastic waste in Ghana. *Arcada University Of Applied Sciences. Degree Thesis Plastics Technology* 2012.
- [25] Shamey R.; Sinha K. A review of degradation of nylon 6.6 as a result of exposure to environmental conditions. *Rev. Prog. Color.* 33 (2003), 93-107.
- [26] Achhammer B.G.; Reinhart F.W.; Kline G.M. Mechanism of the Degradation of Polyamides. *Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards* Vol. 46, No. 5, May 1951, 391-421.
- [27] Pelin C.E.; Fikai A.; Andronescu E.; Stefan A.; Pelin G. Recycling and reusing polyamide 6 extruded waste products to manufacture carbon fiber based composites. *Annals of the Academy of Romanian Scientists Online Series on Physics and Chemistry Sciences* Volume 2, Number 2/2017. ISSN 2537 – 4761.
- [28] Recycled plastics make inroads in automotive applications. *Recycling Today, News and Information for Recycling Professionals.* June 1, 2017.
- [29] Polyamide recycling. *Greener INDUSTRY*, available online: <http://www.greener-industry.org.uk/pages/nylon/8nylonPM3.htm>

- [30] Singha R.; Kumara R.; Ranjana N.; Penna R.; Fraternali F. On the recyclability of polyamide for sustainable composite structures in civil engineering. *Composite Structures*, Volume 184, 15 January 2018, 704-713.
- [31] Polyamide 6 (PA6) NH (CH₂)₅CO Recycling. AZO Materials. December 2012.
- [32] Recycling. America's Plastics Makers, AutomotivePlastics. Available online: <https://plastics-car.com/FAQs/Recycling.html>
- [33] Miller L.; Soulliere K.; Sawyer-Beaulieu S.; Tseng S.; Tam E. Challenges and Alternatives to Plastics Recycling in the Automotive Sector. *Materials* 2014, 7, 5883-5902. doi:10.3390/ma7085883
- [34] Automotive Metal Market Analysis By Product (Aluminum, Steel, Magnesium), By Application (Body Structure, Power Train, Suspension), By End-use, And Segment Forecasts, 2018 – 2025.
- [35] George P.E. Top 5 Materials Used in Auto Manufacturing. Howstuffwork, available online: <https://auto.howstuffworks.com/under-the-hood/auto-manufacturing/5-materials-used-in-auto-manufacturing.htm>
- [36] Trends In Steel Usage In The Automotive Industry. *Forbes*, May 2015.
- [37] Orłowicz A.W.; Mróz M.; Tupaj M.; Trytek A. Materials Used in the Automotive Industry. Published quarterly as the organ of the Foundry Commission of the Polish Academy of Sciences. ISSN (1897-3310), Volume 15, Issue 2/2015, 75 – 78.
- [38] Leblanc R. An introduction to metal recycling. An overview of metal recycling, its importance and recycling processes. *The balance small business* 2018, available online: <https://www.thebalancesmb.com/an-introduction-to-metal-recycling-4057469>.
- [39] Steel Recycling: scrap is a valuable raw material. EUROFER, The European Steel Association.
- [40] Steel Recycling Principles and Practice. AZO Materials. December 2012.

- [41] Pozo Arcos B., Balkenende A.R., Bakker C.A. and Sundin E. (2018) PRODUCT DESIGN FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY: FUNCTIONAL RECOVERY ON FOCUS, In DS 92: Proceedings of the DESIGN 2018 15th International Design Conference, pp 2727-2738.
- [42] Kimura, F. (1999), "Life Cycle Design for Inverse Manufacturing", Environmentally Conscious Design and Inverse Manufacturing Conference Proceedings, p. 995.
- [43] Coulibaly, A., Houssin, R. and Mutel, B. (2008), "Maintainability and safety indicators at design stage for mechanical products", Computers in Industry, Vol. 59 No. 5, pp. 438–449.
- [44] Go, T.F., Wahab, D.A. and Hishamuddin, H. (2015), "Multiple generation life-cycles for product sustainability: The way forward", Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 95, pp. 16–29.
- [45] Pamminger, R., Kuso, S., Wimmer, W. and Podhardsky, G. (2017), "Re-design of a digital voice recorder to meet the needs of circular economy-Status analysis", 2016 Electronics Goes Green 2016+, EGG 2016.
- [46] Sundin, E. and Bras, B. (2005), "Making functional sales environmentally and economically beneficial through product remanufacturing", Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 13 No. 9, pp. 913–925.
- [47] RIC (2016), RIC001.1-2016: Specifications for the Process of Remanufacturing, American National Standard - ANSI approved.

